

A note, with additional information about over-dispersion, to my review “Basic features of the analysis of germination data with generalized linear mixed models” published on *Data* (5:6)

Alberto Gianinetti

In my review (Gianinetti 2020), over-dispersion is illustrated in the context of germination tests, and the use of random intercept models is suggested to address it. However, it is worth noticing that several options exist to account for unit-level uniqueness, the cause of over-dispersion, in the binomial GzLMM (Stroup 2013a; Faretto et al. 2018). In particular, in the field of ecology, two models, the quasi-binomial and the Beta-binomial, are sometimes used to cope with over-dispersion, in addition to random intercept models (Harrison 2015). Although such models ought not to be necessary for germination tests, researchers in the agricultural sciences should at least be aware of their existence. Here are some considerations on this aspect.

In general, over-dispersion among replicates can be tackled with three main approaches (Stroup 2013b; Harrison 2015; Faretto et al. 2018): a constant scale parameter, multiplicative of the binomial variance, can simply be introduced to account for the unexplained over-dispersion in a so-called quasi-binomial model, in which only standard errors and, therefore, significances are corrected accordingly, because of greater uncertainty of estimates than theoretically expected (while the estimates of the linear parameters are not affected); or, a Beta-binomial model (that is, a model whose marginal distribution is obtained as a standard Beta mixture of binomial distributions) is used, assuming that p_i is conditionally Beta distributed (on the data scale) rather than Gaussian; or, the experimental units can be considered the observable source of random variation in the linear predictor, and this effect is modeled as a random intercept (on the linear scale) with a conditional, or a quasi-marginal, model.

The adoption of a quasi-binomial model is a generic solution that can fit real observations only for simple data structures (Stroup 2013b; Faretto et al. 2018). More interestingly, a standard Beta distribution is parametrized so that its mean corresponds to the binomial probability, p_i , and its variance is related to the binomial variance through a dispersion parameter that models p_i as a variable, continuous in the open (0,1) interval, randomly drawn from a standard Beta distribution for every experimental unit. In this way, a standard Beta distribution is appropriate to represent a random distribution of probabilities, and, therefore, a Beta-binomial model is specifically suited when the binomial probability, p_i , is itself a continuous random variable in the interval (0,1) (Faretto et al. 2018). Thus, a Beta distribution can be used when p_i represents the probability of germination in a heterogeneous seed lot (Crowder 1978; Bould 1984). However, both G-side and R-side covariance structures can be problematic to model for two-parameter non-Gaussian distributions like the Beta, at present (Stroup 2013b; Stroup et al. 2018). Moreover, the Beta-binomial model does not permit proportions equal to 0 or 1, and, therefore, all the observations with such values are ignored when fitting this model. Not only, in fact, means must lie in the (0,1) interval, but the BLUP is avoided because the over-dispersion is assumed to be inherent to the data, rather than a nuisance; that is, the observation made on each plate is considered to be the best estimate of an individual p_i value, which varies among plates, rather than an estimate among others of a unique p_i , shared by all the plates of a given group (i.e., data cell). Hence, there is no ‘shrinkage’ that can move extreme data off the limits, and, therefore, not even 0 and 1 individual values can be translated to the linked scale. Managing 0s and 100% is of paramount importance in the application of the Beta-binomial model.

On the other hand, a random intercept model (aka observation-level random effect model) is the most explicit way to account for the extra variability observed at the level of the experimental units, and it can be applied to a wider range of possible data structures. For example, the Beta-binomial model, like the quasi-binomial model, uses a dispersion parameter to scale the binomial variance; this parameter, however, is assumed to be the same (on the data scale) for the whole modeled dataset. If the extra variance is not

constant across groups the standard errors and, therefore, significances are then biased. A random intercept model can, instead, easily handle heterogeneous dispersion across groups (on the linear scale).

Although, in the presence of over-dispersion, random intercept models perform poorly with data generated from a Beta-binomial mixture model (Harrison 2015), the fact that germination data can be interpreted as arising from a threshold process (Gianinetti and Cohn 2007; Bradford 2018), where the linear binomial response represents a normally distributed latent random variable (or a random mix of several latent normal distributions), supports the use of a probit random intercept model for this kind of data (McCulloch 1994). In this respect, for germination data obtained from a seed batch showing in-range heterogeneity, a Beta-binomial model ought to match a random intercept model inasmuch as the standard Beta distribution of p_i on the data scale approximates the normal distribution of probit p_i on the linear scale. The former is, indeed, more flexible (and, therefore, more generic) than the latter, and, thus, the former can always accommodate data that, in reality, follow the latter, but not vice-versa (though 0s and 100% that pertain to non-0 and non-100% means, respectively, have to be properly managed in the Beta-binomial model, for example using an adjustment). More work on this aspect is needed, anyway.

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